

GENERAL VIEW OF THE MANAGEMENT BY OBJECTIVES

AMAÇLARA GÖRE YÖNETİMİN GENEL GÖRÜNÜMÜ

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ABSTRACT

The matter of management by objectives, initially proposed by the renowned management scholar Peter F. Drucker in the 1950s, is sometimes considered within contemporary management techniques, and at times it is examined in issues such as executive or organization development. Initially conceived as a performance evaluation technique aimed at enhancing workplace efficiency and productivity, the management by objectives later evolved into an integrative tool contributing to the transformation of individual goals into organizational objectives. Over time, the management by objectives started to play a role in strategic planning processes and has continued to maintain its popularity for a certain period. In this study, through a literature review, the conceptual content of management by objectives has been reviewed to include up-to-date information from the literature. In conclusion, management by objectives remains one of the significant management tools, although its effectiveness may vary depending on the country, sector, or type of business. Recommendations for business life were given. Besides, directions for further research were presented.

Keywords: Drucker, Objective, MBO, Business History, Management History.

ÖZET

Ünlü yönetim bilimci Peter F. Drucker tarafından 1950'li yıllarda ortaya atılan amaçlara göre yönetim konusunun kimi zaman çağdaş yönetim teknikleri kapsamında ele alındığı, kimi zaman ise yönetici veya örgüt geliştirme gibi konular bağlamında incelendiği bilinmektedir. İş yaşamındaki etkinlik ve verimliliği arttırmak amacıyla başlangıçta bir performans değerlendirme tekniği olarak ortaya çıkan amaçlara göre yönetim yaklaşımı, sonrasında bireysel amaçların örgütsel amaçlara dönüştürülmesine katkı sağlayan bir bütünleştirme aracı dönüşmüştür. Zamanla stratejik planlama süreçlerinde de rol oynamaya başlayan amaçlara göre yönetim yaklaşımı belirli bir süre popülerliğini korumaya devam etmiştir. Bu çalışmada yazın taraması ile amaçlara göre yönetim konusunun kavramsal içeriği yazındaki güncel bilgileri içerecek şekilde derlenmiştir. Netice itibarıyla, amaçlara göre yönetim konusunun halen önemli yönetim araçlarından birisi olduğu ancak, zaman zaman ülke, sektör veya iş türlerine göre bu yaklaşımdan elde edilen etkinlik düzeyinin farklılık gösterdiği anlaşılmaktadır. Çalışmada iş yaşamına yönelik tavsiyeler verilmiştir. Ayrıca, gelecekte yapılacak araştırmalar için öneriler sunulmuştur.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Drucker, Amaç, AGY, İşletme Tarihi, Yönetim Tarihi.

1. Introduction

The management by objectives, one of the essential management techniques in the field of business administration, was first introduced by Peter F. Drucker in the 1950s (Drucker, 1954; Rahman et al., 2020). Management by objectives emerges as a psychological tool that enhances an employee's self-confidence by conveying that they are not just a number within the organization but a human being. Additionally, it can also serve as an organizational development tool that promotes self-improvement due to reasons such as employees determining their own needs and not having them forcibly imposed by others (Güney, 2017; Koçel, 2013; Ntanos & Boulouta, 2012).

In literature, management by objectives is also referred to by various names such as goals and results-based management, management by objectives and results, goal-oriented management, and management based on shared objectives. Initially, management by objectives was primarily considered a performance evaluation method, but later evolved into a modern management technique and found application (Antoni, 2005; Ivancevich, 1974; Tortop et al., 2007).

According to the management by objectives approach, individuals who determine their own goals tend to take ownership of them more, resulting in increased motivation and job performance. Therefore, it is more rational for managers to make decisions about the goals with their subordinates rather than telling them what the goals should be (Genç, 2017). Consequently, unlike other management techniques, the management by objectives approach is seen as developing a separate management technique that evaluates management practices around objectives. The concept of management by objectives, introduced in the 1950s, has become increasingly important in businesses as goals have gained more significance over time (Çelik & Şimşek, 2013).

When it comes to the holistic historical development process, it is clear that the management by objectives approach is less popular than, at least, other management techniques. Notably, the lower preference for management by objectives in the public sector compared to the private sector in terms of finding its application (Yıldız & Çobanoğlu, 2016) can be cited as an example of this situation.

On the one hand, gaining popularity since the 1950s, but on the other hand, showing less effectiveness than expected in certain countries, sectors, or types of businesses has made the management by objectives topic intriguing. For this problematic issue related to management by objectives to become apparent, it is also essential to understand the conceptual content of this topic correctly. Indeed, in this study, the concept of management by objectives has been addressed in a way that includes the current information in the literature.

In the subsequent sections of the study, the concept of management by objectives is explained, followed by the historical development of the management by objectives approach. Then, the features, stages, benefits, and limitations of management by objectives are discussed. Recommendations for the business environment are provided in the study. Additionally, directions for further research are presented.

2. Literature Overview

2.1. Conceptual Definition of Management by Objectives

Peter F. Drucker's concept of management by objectives is expressed as follows: A management principle that provides a complete form to the authority and responsibilities of individuals required by organizations, while also aligning efforts and views towards a common direction, harmonizing personal goals with shared objectives, and fostering teamwork (Çelik & Şimşek, 2013; Drucker, 1954; Genç, 2017; Kyriakopoulos, 2012). In this process, which forms the essence of the management by objectives approach, managers and employees in an organization jointly determine the objectives they want to achieve, collectively decide on their areas of responsibility and the methods they will use, and examine together whether these objectives and outcomes have been performed at specific intervals (Greenwood, 1981; Rodgers & Hunter, 1991).

In the management by objectives approach, employees contemplate their job and personal goals for the upcoming period. Subsequently, they independently compiled a list of objectives for this period. The employee then presents this list to their manager, and through mutual discussion, an agreement is reached regarding the employee's objectives for the following year. Additionally, there is a mutual understanding of the criteria that will be used to measure the achievement of the defined objectives. Ultimately, the employee works towards achieving the set objectives. During this process, an approach involves intervening as needed rather than closely monitoring at every stage. Finally, a more formal review is conducted at the end of the period, and new objectives are set in collaboration with the employee. This way, the entire process is reinitiated for the next period. This process is what we refer to as management by objectives (Güney, 2017).

Management by objectives, based on the principle of managers setting goals and objectives and working collaboratively with employees to achieve them, includes detailed job descriptions among its core objectives. In other words, management by objectives is a management approach that assigns the task and responsibility of determining the organization's goals, preparing activity plans to reach those goals, ensuring coordination between activities, monitoring activities, and evaluating the data obtained to the managers. This management style empowers managers by giving them the authority and responsibility to achieve these goals, promotes teamwork, and aligns individual goals with organizational objectives. Additionally, it is a dynamic system that allows managers to enhance their skills and engage in self-assessment (Güney, 2017; Yıldız & Çobanoğlu, 2016).

This approach has emerged as an essential management approach used to increase productivity, optimize business processes, and measure success within the workplace. In other words, management by objectives involves defining objectives set by an individual or organization, developing strategies to achieve these objectives, monitoring performance, and striving to reach the established goals (Dinesh & Palmer, 1998; Fields, 1974; Rahman et al., 2020). In this context, management by objectives is better described as a technique or approach aimed at enhancing the effectiveness of management activities rather than merely explaining cause-and-effect relationships among management events. Therefore, it is more appropriate to characterize management by objectives as a tool or approach that seeks to improve the efficiency of management activities (Çelik & Şimşek, 2013; Fields, 1974; Koçel, 2013).

Briefly, management by objectives is a dynamic system that combines establishing an organization's development goals with the ability for both managers and employees to contribute to and improve themselves. It provides a common understanding of what needs to be done by the manager and the employee. It enables the proper organization of a manager's work and interaction with employees to fulfill their roles effectively. Management by objectives has established itself as a management technique that serves as a tool for the supervision function (Çelik & Şimşek, 2013; Rodgers & Hunter, 1991).

2.2. Historical Development of Management by Objectives

As its content suggests, management by objectives represents a process. The management by objectives approach is about implementing this practice within an organization. Indeed, the historical development of management by objectives can be divided into three stages. These stages can be listed as follows (Çelik & Şimşek, 2013; Koçel, 2013):

2.2.1. Performance Evaluation

In the 1950s, management by objectives was primarily perceived and implemented as a performance evaluation system. In other words, the performance evaluation aspect of management by objectives prevailed during its early years. It was recognized that personality-based evaluations were subjective and not motivating, leading to the adopting of result-oriented evaluations. During this period, managers were assessed based on their ability to achieve predetermined objectives. However, it became evident that a narrow interpretation of management by objectives failed to capture the mutual relationships and interactions between the goals of employees working in various departments and the organization's objectives (Çelik & Şimşek, 2013; Fields, 1974).

2.2.2. Integration

During this stage, the practice of management by objectives serves the function of achieving coherence between organizational objectives and employees' individual goals. Management by objectives, a part of the management process, had a short-term perspective during this phase. It is known that the desire to implement the program came from the top management of the organization rather than the personnel department at this time (Çelik & Şimşek, 2013; Genç, 2017).

2.2.3. Long-Term (Strategic) Planning

In this stage, the primary objective is to fulfill the long-term goals of both individuals and the organization. Consequently, during this development phase, management by objectives becomes part of strategic planning. Long-term goals are determined, and long-term plans are established, focusing on aligning the identification and planning of short-term objectives on this foundational basis (Çelik & Şimşek, 2013; Fields, 1974; Howell, 1970).

2.3. Features of Management by Objectives

To better understand the conceptual definition of management by objectives and grasp its functions, it's beneficial to be aware of the features associated with this approach. In relevant studies, the key features of management by objectives (MBO) are often described as follows (Çelik & Şimşek, 2013; Genç, 2017; Koçel, 2013; Parlak, 2013; Yıldız & Çobanoğlu, 2016):

- i. MBO represents a philosophy.
- ii. MBO is a tool for planning and control.
- iii. MBO provides an opportunity for participation in management.
- iv. MBO serves as a performance evaluation tool.
- v. MBO motivates individuals involved in decision-making and implementation mechanisms.
- vi. MBO is a process that allows for personnel development.

2.4. Stages of Management by Objectives

The management by objectives approach is implemented as a four-stage process. These stages are as follows:

2.4.1. Setting Objectives

The first stage of management by objectives is the establishment of clear, measurable, and achievable objectives in the organization's core areas of activity. It's crucial to define specific, measurable, and quantitative objectives. The process of setting objectives begins at the top management level of the organization and trickles down in the form of an objective hierarchy to the lower levels of the organization. This way, the primary objectives set by top management cascade down into more detailed sub-objectives (targets) at lower levels, aligning the entire organization toward a specific goal (Çelik & Şimşek, 2013; Krlev, 2011).

In the process of setting objectives within management by objectives, three categories can be identified: the determination of long-term (strategic) objectives, the establishment of specific organizational objectives, and the setting of department-level objectives. Strategic planning is distinguished from other types of planning by its extended time horizon, consideration of environmental conditions, and holistic examination of the organization. In the process of determining specific organizational objectives, the objectives set in the strategic plan are translated into operational plans. In the process of setting department-level objectives, the organizational objectives defined in the first two stages are broken down into specific sub-objectives for various departments (Çelik & Şimşek, 2013; Genç, 2017).

2.4.2. Activity Planning

The second essential stage of management by objectives involves the development of activity plans. Activity planning is concerned with determining how the objectives set in the strategic plan, which have been broken down to the department and individual levels, will be achieved. This stage determines which activities will be carried out, how, where, when, and by whom. Plans are created by departments accordingly. Activity planning is prepared by managers who are responsible for achieving the objectives. This process transforms a manager from someone who merely executes what is told to them into a decision-maker involved in determining what needs to be done to achieve the objectives. Therefore, during this process, both subordinates and superiors will enhance their skills, and the organization will benefit more from these individuals' abilities (Çelik & Şimşek, 2013; Genç, 2017; Koçel, 2013).

2.4.3. *Implementation and Control*

The third fundamental stage of management by objectives, implementation and control, establishes the connection between putting plans into action and achieving objectives. In this stage, managers are responsible for implementing the plans and taking measures in case of any deviations. This phase of management by objectives is about giving individuals the opportunity to showcase their skills and abilities, creating an environment that allows for self-improvement, and aligning personal objectives with organizational objectives. This set of activities not only motivates the manager but also provides an opportunity for self-assessment and, thus, personal development. The manager, by evaluating the outcomes of their decisions based on feedback from implementation, investigates the reasons behind any deviations if they exist (Çelik & Şimşek, 2013; Genç, 2017; Koçel, 2013).

2.4.4. *Periodic Evaluations*

The final stage of management by objectives involves determining the extent to which the established objectives have been achieved. In this stage, both the subordinate and the superior regularly review the subordinate's objectives and the results achieved, just as in the stage of setting objectives. Based on this, the superior evaluates the subordinate. This evaluation is communicated to the subordinate and serves as input to sub-systems such as rewards, training, and more. Additionally, this evaluation forms a basis for the first stage of the management by objectives process, which is the process of setting objectives (Çelik & Şimşek, 2013; Koçel, 2013).

2.5. **Benefits of Management by Objectives**

The management by objectives (MBO) approach offers several key benefits, which can be summarized as follows (Çelik & Şimşek, 2013; Koçel, 2013; Tosi & Carroll, 1968):

- i. MBO injects vitality into hierarchical organizational structures. This vitality is achieved by encouraging organizational members to engage in organizational activities personally. This, in turn, creates an environment that enhances the effectiveness of these structures.
- ii. MBO makes the planning and control functions more effective. Since MBO specifies where and how to reach the objectives in detail, it simplifies the control process.
- iii. MBO allows managers to have more self-control. When managers know what results need to be achieved and when they become less reliant on superiors' directives to organize their activities.
- iv. MBO helps clarify what subordinates and superiors expect from each other.
- v. MBO compels managers to engage in planning.
- vi. MBO facilitates the more accessible and more timely diagnosis of problems.

These benefits contribute to enhanced organizational performance, improved communication and coordination, and greater employee motivation and involvement in goal achievement.

2.6. Limitations of Management by Objectives

The first information that should be noted about the limited aspects of management by objectives is that this approach does not find solutions to all problems. Management by objectives (MBO) may face some limiting factors, both due to the reasons arising from the system itself, the structure of the organization in which it is applied, and the managers. These can be summarized as follows (Çelik & Şimşek, 2013; Fields, 1974; Howell, 1970; Koçel, 2013; Tosi & Carroll, 1968):

- i. MBO focuses exclusively on a management model determined by objectives.
- ii. The success of MBO is highly dependent on top management's commitment and involvement.
- iii. Difficulties in setting clear objectives can hinder the success of MBO.
- iv. There are natural limitations to MBO due to the delegation of authority it recommends.
- v. MBO can increase the volume of written communication and reporting.
- vi. MBO can be costly in terms of financial resources and time.
- vii. MBO may not equally serve every purpose for which it is managed.

These limitations highlight that while management by objectives can be a valuable tool, it may not suit every organization or situation. Considering these limitations is necessary when implementing management by objectives to maximize its benefits and mitigate its shortcomings.

3. Conclusions

Peter F. Drucker, renowned for his significant contributions to the field of management science, emphasized in one of his books that what management needs to research, develop, and learn to experiment with is the creation of an organization suitable for the task (Drucker, 1999, 2014). It can be understood that the management by objectives approach, introduced by Drucker himself in the 1950s, is based on this context (Drucker, 1954, 2012).

Organizations consist of systems that aim not to remain inactive, to constantly produce, and to try to make profits in line with their goals (Can & Aydın; Robbins & Judge, 2021). It is a widely accepted fact that in periods of intensified competition, effective management techniques are essential for the success of organizations (Irk & Döven, 2018; Porter, 1990). From this perspective, management by objectives has emerged as a management approach that enables organizations to set their goals, focus on these goals, and continually make progress.

Objectives are fundamental elements that determine where organizations want to go and what they want to achieve. Accurately defining objectives ensures that organizations reflect their missions and visions. Objectives serve as a guide for all employees of organizations and establish a framework for collaboration and teamwork. Furthermore, objectives allow organizations to measure their performance and assess results, facilitating continuous improvement (Gagné, 2018; Gross, 1969). Based on these realities, it is evident that the management by objectives approach, which is built upon objectives, contributes significantly to the business life.

When looking at the literature in the context of recommendations for the business life, it is understood that the management by objectives approach offers several advantages to organizations. In this context, management by objectives first provides organizations with clarity and a focal point. All employees focus on the organization's primary objectives and work together to achieve these goals. Furthermore, management by objectives helps organizations improve their performance. Since objectives are measurable, organizations can track their progress and make adjustments when necessary, increasing efficiency. As a result, management by objectives emerges as a powerful tool to enhance the success of organizations.

On the other hand, other perspectives need to be expressed concerning the management by objectives approach in the business life context. In this regard, it is understood that there is no definitive view that management by objectives is always successful. Indeed, various sources in the literature acknowledge that management by objectives is not a one-size-fits-all solution to every management problem (Çelik & Şimşek, 2013; Koçel, 2013). Furthermore, there are opinions suggesting that management by objectives is less preferred in the public sector compared to the private sector (Yıldız & Çobanoğlu, 2016). Therefore, it would be prudent for managers to be aware of the limitations of any management tool or technique and consider the country, industry, and type of business they are involved in.

In the context of recommendations for further research, it is understood that there are gaps in the field of management by objectives. Firstly, it should be emphasized that management by objectives has mainly been approached from a philosophical perspective until now. Therefore, there is a need for applied research that examines the issue of management by objectives at the organizational and sectoral levels, focusing on different levels of managers and employees, and designed with both quantitative and qualitative research. Investigating the subject of management by objectives through applied research will also contribute to filling the gaps in understanding the advantages and disadvantages of this approach.

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Geniřletilmiş Özet

İřletme yönetimi alanındaki önemli yönetim tekniklerinden birisi olan amaçlara göre yönetim ilk defa 1950’li yıllarda Peter F. Drucker tarafından ortaya atılmıştır (Drucker, 1954; Rahman vd., 2020). Amaçlara göre yönetim, iřletmelerin ihtiyacı olan kişilerin yetki ve sorumluluklarına tam bir Őekil veren, aynı zamanda uğraşı ve görüşlere ortak bir yön çizen, kişisel amaçları bu ortak amaçla uyumlařtıran ve ekip çalıřması yaratan bir yönetim ilkesi Őeklinde tanımlanmaktadır (Çelik & ŐimŐek, 2013; Genç, 2017; Kyriakopoulos, 2012). Bu yaklaşım bir örgütteki yöneticilerin ve çalıřanların ulaşmak istedikleri amaçları birlikte belirledikleri, sorumluluk alanlarını ve kullanacakları yol ve yöntemleri birlikte kararlařtırdıkları ve belirli dönemlerde bu amaçlar ve sonuçların gerçekteleşip gerçekteleşmediğini birlikte inceledikleri bir sürece karşılık gelmektedir (Greenwood, 1981; Rodgers & Hunter, 1991).

Bir yandan 1950’li yıllardan sonra artış gösteren bir popülerliğe ulaşması ancak, diđer yandan bazı ülke, sektör veya iş türlerinde beklenildiği kadar etkinlik göstermemesi amaçlara göre yönetim konusunu dikkat çekici bir hale getirmiştir. Amaçlara göre yönetim konusuna ait bu sorunsalın netlik kazanması için bu konunun kavramsal içeriğinin doğru bir Őekilde anlaşılmasının da önemi bulunmaktadır. Nitekim bu çalıřmada amaçlara göre yönetim konusu yazındaki güncel bilgileri içerecek Őekilde derlenmiştir.

Amaçlara göre yönetim, iş yaşamı içerisinde verimliliği arttırmak, iş süreçlerini en iyi hale getirmek ve başarıyı ölçmek için kullanılan önemli bir yönetim yaklaşımını ifade etmektedir. Bařka bir anlatımla amaçlara göre yönetim, bir bireyin veya örgütün belirlediği amaçları tanımlama, bu amaçlara ulaşma stratejileri geliřtirme, performansı izleme ve hedeflere ulaşma sürecini belirtmektedir (Dinesh & Palmer, 1998; Fields, 1974; Rahman vd., 2020). Bu bağlamda amaçlara göre yönetim, yönetim olayları arasındaki sebep - sonuç ilişkilerini açıklayan bir görüşten çok, yönetim sürecini daha etkin hale getirmeye çalıřan bir araçtır. Dolayısıyla amaçlara göre yönetimi, yönetim faaliyetlerinin etkinliğini arttırmaya yönelmiş bir teknik veya yaklaşım olarak nitelemek daha uygun olmaktadır (Çelik & ŐimŐek, 2013; Fields, 1974; Koçel, 2013).

Kuruluşun geliřme hedeflerinin saptanması ve harekete geçilmesi için katkı sunma felsefesine dayanan amaçlara göre yönetim yaklaşımı, yönetici ve çalıřanın kendilerini geliřtirmesi süreciyle ilerleyen dinamik bir sistemdir. Amaçlara göre yönetim, yöneticinin ve çalıřanın ortak bir akılla ne yapacağını bildirmektedir. Yöneticinin işinin gereği gibi örgütlenmesini ve çalıřanlarla etkileşimde bulunarak görevlerini yerine getirmesini mümkün kılmaktadır. Bu yönleriyle amaçlara göre yönetim, denetleme işlevinin bir aracı olarak tutunmuş bir yönetim tekniği olarak ortaya çıkmaktadır (Çelik & ŐimŐek, 2013; Rodgers & Hunter, 1991).

Amaçlar, örgütlerin nereye gitmek istediklerini ve neyi başarmak istediklerini belirleyen temel unsurlardır. Amaçların doğru bir Őekilde tanımlanması, örgütlerin misyonlarını ve vizyonlarını yansıtmalarını sağlamaktadır. Amaçlar, örgütlerin tüm çalıřanları için bir rehber görevi görmekte ve birlikte çalıřma ve işbirliği için bir çerçeve oluşturmaktadır. Amaçlar ayrıca örgütlerin performansını ölçmelerini ve sonuçları deđerlendirmelerini sağlamaktadır. Bu da örgütlerin sürekli olarak kendilerini geliřtirmelerine yardımcı olmaktadır (Gagné, 2018; Gross, 1969). Bu gerçeklikler üzerine kurulan amaçlara göre yönetim yaklaşımının iş yaşamı için pek çok katkısı olduğu açıktır.

İş yaşamına öneriler bağlamında yazına genel olarak bakıldığında amaçlara göre yönetim yaklaşımının örgütler için bir dizi avantaj sunduğu anlaşılmaktadır. Bu bağlamda, amaçlara göre yönetim ilk olarak, örgütler için bir netlik ve odak noktası sağlamaktadır. Tüm çalışanlar, örgütün ana hedeflerine odaklanmakta ve bu hedeflere ulaşmak için birlikte çalışmaktadırlar. Ayrıca, amaçlara göre yönetim örgütlerin performansını iyileştirmelerine yardımcı olmaktadır. Amaçlar ölçülebilir olduğundan, örgütler ilerlemelerini izleyebilmekte ve gerektiğinde ayarlamalar yapabilmektedirler. Bu da verimliliği arttırmaktadır. Sonuç olarak, amaçlara göre yönetim örgütlerin başarısını arttırmak için güçlü bir araç olarak kendisini göstermektedir.

Diğer yandan, amaçlara göre yönetim yaklaşımı ile ilgili iş yaşamına yönelik olarak ifade edilmesi gereken başka bakış açıları da vardır. Bu açıdan, amaçlara göre yönetim yaklaşımının her zaman başarılı olduğu ile ilgili kesin bir görüşün olmadığı anlaşılmaktadır. Nitekim yazındaki farklı kaynaklar tarafından amaçlara göre yönetimin her yönetim sorununa çözüm getiren bir teknik olmadığı kabul edilmektedir (Çelik & Şimşek, 2013; Koçel, 2013). Bununla birlikte, amaçlara göre yönetimin özel sektöre kıyasla kamu sektöründe daha az tercih edildiğine yönelik görüşler de bulunmaktadır (Yıldız & Çobanoğlu, 2016). Dolayısıyla, yöneticilerin kullandıkları her yönetim aracının veya tekniğinin sınırlarının farkında olarak hareket etmeleri ve içinde buldukları ülke, sektör ve iş türünü dikkate almaları doğru olacaktır.

Gelecekte yapılacak araştırmalara öneriler bağlamında amaçlara göre yönetim konusuyula ilgili boşluklar olduğu anlaşılmaktadır. Bu noktada öncelikle ifade edilmesi gereken husus amaçlara göre yönetim konusunun bu zamana kadar çoğunlukla felsefi yönüyle ele alınmasıdır. Dolayısıyla, amaçlara göre yönetim konusunu örgüt ve sektör düzeyinde inceleyecek, farklı seviyelerdeki yöneticiler ve çalışanlar üzerine odaklanacak, nicel ve nitel araştırma desenleriyle tasarlanmış olan uygulamalı araştırmalara ihtiyaç olduğu söylenebilir. Amaçlara göre yönetim konusunun uygulamalı araştırmalar üzerinden incelenmesi, aynı zamanda bu konunun avantaj ve dezavantajlarının neler olduğuyla ilgili boşlukların giderilmesine de katkı sağlayacaktır.

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